

TABLE I—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF R_pH AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF ITS METAL COMPLEXES

Ligand	pk*	Metal (II)	log K_1	log K_2	Standard deviation (Range)
R_pH	5.04 ± 0.02	Cu(II)	2.01 ± 0.03	1.57 ± 0.03	$\pm 0.013 (0.01 < \bar{n}_R < 1.10)$
	$[\sigma = \pm 0.009 (0.3 < \bar{n}_H < 1.0)]$	UO ₂ (II)	3.62 ± 0.05	3.20 ± 0.05	$\pm 0.022 (0.20 < \bar{n}_H < 0.80)$

Discussion

The potentiometric study in mixed solvents was made following the procedure developed by Van Uitert and Hass¹⁹. Acid concentration (h) of any water-dioxan mixture was determined by graphical extrapolation^{20,21} of plot of pH value against (-log h).

The pk* value of the ligand R_pH indicates that it is a weak acid. During titration of Cu(II) in presence of R_pH (being in large excess) with NaOH solution, $\bar{n}_R$ could not be obtained beyond 1.3 due to earlier precipitation. The stability constant data indicate that the stability order is UO₂(II) > Cu(II). Formation curves were obtained on plotting $\bar{n}_{RCalc}$ and $\bar{n}_{R(Exp)}$ values against corresponding p_{RD} values. The experimental curve is in good agreement with the calculated one within the region $0.01 < \bar{n}_R < 1.10$ and $0.2 < \bar{n}_R < 0.80$ in the cases of Cu(II) and UO₂(II) complexes respectively. In dilute solution, the experimental formation curve of UO₂(II) complex agrees well with the calculated curve upto $\bar{n}_R$ value equal to 1.15. Deviations of the experimental formation curve from the calculated one outside these regions indicate that the course of reaction at the later stages of complex formation (pH > 5) may be somewhat different from these represented by equations (2) and (3). The formation of polynuclear complexes of UO₂(II) is not completely ruled out at the later stages of complex formation.

By potentiometric titration of R_pH in presence of Ni(II) and Co(II), the formation of complex compounds of Ni(II) and Co(II) is not indicated.

Acknowledgement

Authors are grateful to University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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Synthesis and Reactions of 4-Picolyl Magnesium Iodide

V. K. GOEL, R. K. PANDEY and B. C. JOSHI*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur

Manuscript received 16 June 1976, revised 11 October 1976; accepted 30 December 1976

4-Picolyl magnesium iodide(I) was prepared by reacting ethyl magnesium iodide with 4-picoline in connection with the synthesis of 6,7-(4', 5'-pyrido)-morphans. The structure of I was proved by its reactions with benzaldehyde and acetone when 1-(pyridyl-4)-2-phenyl ethanol-2 (II) and 1-(pyridyl-4)-2-methyl-propanol-2 (III) were obtained.

*For correspondence: Chemistry Department, University of Garhwal, Srinagar-Garhwal (U.P.)

The assigned structures II and III were confirmed from the elemental analyses, IR and PMR spectral data.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The PMR spectra were recorded in Perkin Elmer R12B spectrometer using TMS as internal reference standard and CCl₄ as solvent.

4-Picolyl magnesium iodide (I)

Ethyl magnesium iodide (ethyl iodide, 0.05M; magnesium, 0.05M and diethyl ether, 100 ml) was added dropwise within 15 min to a solution of 4-picoline (0.05M in 100 ml dry di-n-butyl ether)^{1,2}. The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously at the elevated temperature 120-30° for 4 hr when a heterogeneous red brown oil (I) was obtained.

1-(Pyridyl-4)-2-phenyl ethanol-2-(II) and 1-(Pyridyl-4)-2-methyl-propanol-2 (III)

Benzaldehyde and acetone were added to 4-picolyl-magnesium iodide separately at 0-5° with continuous stirring for 5 hr. The reaction mixtures were left over night and then again stirred for 1 hr at 50-60°. The crude products obtained after the usual treatment were separately distilled at 0.5 mm pressure and were identified as II (20% yield, b.p. 150°/0.5 mm, HCl salt-m.p. 210-12°)³ and III (15% yield, b.p. 135°/0.5 mm, HCl salt-m.p. 195°, picrate-m.p. 208°). The purity of these compounds were ascertained through TLC using EtOH : EtOAc : HCOOH (6 : 2 : 2) as mobile phase (Rf's : II, 0.75 ; III, 0.70).

IR spectra : II and III, 3400 cm⁻¹

PMR spectra : II- δ 7.1-7.6, 9H ; δ 3.9-4.4, 3H ; δ 5.85 (broad), 1H

III- δ 7.1-7.6, 4H ; δ 4.05, 2H ; δ 0.95, 6H ; δ 5.90, 1H

Elemental Analyses: Found : C, 66.36 ; H, 5.68 ; N, 5.86%. Calcd for C₁₅H₁₄ONCl (II.HCl) : C, 66.24 ; H, 5.94 ; N, 5.94%

Found : C, 57.56 ; H, 7.24 ; N, 7.32%. Calcd for C₉H₁₄ONCl (III.HCl) : C, 57.60 ; H, 7.46 ; N, 7.46%

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for providing necessary facilities.

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Synergic Extraction of Titanium(IV) in the Presence of Morin and Aniline**

K. SOBHANA and C. P. SAVARIAR*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Kerala 673635, India.

Manuscript received 6 April 1976, revised 23 August 1976, accepted 30 December 1976

MANY methods have been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of titanium¹⁻⁴. However, only few papers have been published on the synergic extraction of the ternary complex of titanium⁵⁻⁷. No work appears to be recorded on the extraction of Ti(IV)-morin chelate in the presence of aniline as synergist. It is observed in the present work that the addition of aniline to the extractant caused a considerable enhancement of the distribution ratio of titanium. Based on this, an accurate and simple extractive-spectrophotometric method is suggested for the determination of titanium(IV).

Experimental

A Bausch & Lomb Spectronic 20, with matched test tubes, was used for absorbance measurements. Toshniwal (India) pH meter was used for measurement of pH.

Titanium solution (1 mg Ti ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of AnalaR potassium titanyl oxalate in double distilled water containing 100 ml of 5N H₂SO₄ and making upto one litre. The metal content per ml was estimated gravimetrically by cupferron⁸.

A 0.05M solution of morin was prepared in 50% alcohol. Further dilutions were made as and when necessary.

All solvents including aniline were purified by distillation.

Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer was used.

*Presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, Roorkee 1975.